

Appendix C: Analysis of individual galaxies

DDO43

Figs.11-12 show the results for DDO43. The orientation angles measured by the TRM fluctuate around a roughly constant value and thus we do not calculate the corrections to $v_\theta(R)$ and $v_R(R)$ due to a possible warp as these are negligible. The radial and transversal velocity component maps, reconstructed by the VRM, show relevant angular anisotropies. Data for the stellar components are not available and we neglect it in the DMD fit: with only one free parameter, γ_g (see Eq.15), we find a good DMD fit. However, we note that for this galaxy, as well as for others where the stellar component has negligible mass (i.e., DDO46, DDO47, and F564-V3), the DMD fit uses only one parameter, while the NFW fit uses two parameters. Thus, it is not surprising that, in the latter case, the reduced χ^2 is smaller. In addition, it is worth noting that the transversal velocity component detected by the VRM is more fluctuating than the circular velocity measured by the VRM. This occurs because fluctuations in the former are perceived as variations in the orientation angles in the latter. This difference between the VRM and TRM results is clearly evident in all cases where the orientation angles vary as a function of scale.

DDO46

DDO46 is similar to DDO43 (Fig.13-14): the orientation angles are roughly constant and the velocity field is characterized by relatively large angular anisotropies. The system is dominated by a radial outflow beyond 100'' and we thus limit the analysis of the transversal component at smaller radii: for $R > 80''$ the effect of the warp, visible in the behavior of the PA, corresponds to the apparent growth of the mean radial velocity profile. Even in this case, as for DDO43, there are no data for the stellar component and we make a single free parameter best fit with the DMD. Note that the DMD fit is worse than the NFW fit: as in the case of DDO43, this is due to the fact that the DMD model has one fewer parameter. Additionally, it is worth noting that the agreement is poorer in the inner region of the disc, while in the outer parts, both models fit the observational data equally well.

DDO47

The results for DDO47 are depicted in Figures 15 to 16. In Figure 15(c), the orientation angles show a clear radial dependence, indicating the presence of a warp in the galaxy. However, the results obtained with the VRM are similar to those obtained with the TRM in the inner disc where the fit with the theoretical models is done. Additionally, the velocity maps reveal significant perturbations in DDO47, corresponding to angular anisotropies, as shown in Figures 16(a) and 16(b). These spatial velocities increase in amplitude with distance from the galaxy's center, a behavior observed in other galaxies in our sample as well. Even in this case, data for the stellar component are not available. Consequently, we perform a fit using the DMD model with a single free parameter. Due to the

limited number of adjustable parameters, the resulting fit may yield a relatively high reduced χ^2 value. For the fitting process, we employ a smoothed fit to the gas velocity v_g using an analytical exponential thin disc model approximation. This approach aims to regularize the behavior of the gas component. However, it is important to note that the absence of stellar component data and the simplicity of the fitting model limit the fit's ability to fully capture the system's intricacies, contributing to the relatively high reduced χ^2 value.

DDO50

The orientation angles for DDO50 (Figs17-18) exhibit a smooth variation with radial distance, indicating the presence of a warp in the galaxy. However, as in the case of DDO47, the results of the VRM and TRM are very close in the inner disc, indicating that the warp does not introduce significant distortions within this range of radial distances. The primary difference lies in the fact that the transversal velocity obtained by the VRM is more fluctuating. Note that we used an overall inclination angle of $i = 49.7^\circ$, whereas Iorio et al. (2017) found a smaller value, $i = 32^\circ$. This difference corresponds to a scaling factor in the rotation curve of $\sin(32^\circ)/\sin(49.7^\circ) \approx 0.7$ (in Fig.7 the Iorio et al. (2017) have been rescaled by such a factor. Clearly, the total mass estimation is affected by this rescaling. However, the ratio between the NFW M_{200} and M_{DMD} remains unchanged. The velocity maps of DDO50 reveal the presence of anisotropic patterns, characterized by localized velocity gradients. These patterns provide further insights into the dynamics of the galaxy, highlighting variations in the velocities across different regions. The goodness of fit for the two mass models, NFW and DMD, is comparable, with the relatively high χ^2 value (~ 2) primarily attributable to the significant fluctuations characterizing the circular velocity.

DDO52

Both orientation angles of DDO52 (see Fig.19-20) exhibit limited variations in the outer regions of the system, while displaying more pronounced changes in the inner regions. This implies that the inner region of the galaxy is likely dominated by velocity gradients rather than a substantial change in the disc's geometry. Indeed, the velocity profile obtained by the VRM is more fluctuating than that measured by the TRM, but both exhibit similar behaviors: the transverse velocity profile detected by the VRM method closely aligns with the rotational velocity measured by the TRM method. This indicates a good agreement between the two methods in capturing the velocity behavior of the system. On the other hand, the rotational velocity that we have found differs from that found by Iorio et al. (2017) because of the different inclination angle used, i.e. $i = 43^\circ$ instead of $i = 55^\circ$ (in Fig.7 the Iorio et al. (2017) have been rescaled by a factor $\sin(55^\circ)/\sin(43^\circ)$). Furthermore, no significant net radial motions are observed; instead, large fluctuations are present, particularly in the outermost regions. Fluctuations in the velocity component profiles correspond to localized velocity anisotropies, which are evident across the entire disc, as

Fig. 11: As Fig.3 but for DDO43

Fig. 12: As Fig.4 but for DDO43

Fig. 13: As Fig.3 but for DDO46.

shown in the 2D maps. These fluctuations may be attributed to various factors influencing the system's dynamics. Finally, we note that the fits with both models yield a similar reduced $\chi^2 \sim 1$, which remains relatively high due to the fluctuations in the velocity profile.

DDO53

The orientation angles of DDO53 exhibit a roughly constant trend with respect to the radius, although they display a fluctuating behavior. The analysis conducted using the VRM interprets that these fluctuations correspond to velocity anisotropies within the galaxy. Indeed, the velocity profile obtained using the VRM is noisier than that measured with the TRM but showing the same trend: this suggests a reasonable agreement between the two methods in capturing the overall velocity behav-

ior of the system. Note that in this case we used the inclination angle $i = 27^\circ$ from Oh et al. (2015) which is smaller than that determined by Iorio et al. (2017) (i.e., $i = 39^\circ$) and thus Fig.7 the Iorio et al. (2017) result have been rescaled. . DDO53 demonstrates an irregular LOS velocity field, as well as an HI intensity map that exhibits local fluctuations (refer to Figs.21-22). Additionally, the LOS velocity dispersion map displays several localized fluctuations as well. These observations indicate complex dynamics within the galaxy, with variations in velocities and intensity across different regions. Regarding the mass model fits, both models show good agreement, with a reduced $\chi^2 \sim 0.5$.

Fig. 14: As Fig.4 but for DDO46.

Fig. 15: As Fig.3 but for DDO47.

Fig. 16: As Fig.4 but for DDO47.

DDO70

The presence of a warp in DDO70 is evident from the smooth variation of the orientation angles from the inner to the outer regions (refer to Figures 23 to 24). In addition to the anisotropies induced by the warp in the reconstructed velocity maps obtained through the VRM method, we observe large anisotropies in the external regions that exhibit a greater amplitude compared to those in the inner regions. This observation is consistent with the structures visible in the H α intensity map and the LOS velocity dispersion map. The two mass models, i.e., the DMD and the NFW, exhibit similar $\chi^2 \sim 2$ values, with the relatively high value attributed to large fluctuations affecting the profile of the circular velocity component.

DDO87

The orientation angles do not exhibit any significant radial trend, indicating that a significant warp is likely not present in this galaxy (see Figures 25-26). However, the velocity maps reveal large angular anisotropies, which align with the fluctuating nature observed in both the H α intensity map and the LOS velocity dispersion map. Even for this galaxy, the velocity profile obtained through the VRM method is similar to, but much more fluctuating than, that resulting from the TRM analysis, as, in the former case, these fluctuations are absorbed into those of the orientation angles. The inclination angle $i = 55.5^\circ$ from Oh et al. (2015) is larger than that determined by Iorio et al. (2017) (i.e., $i = 45^\circ$). The fits using the DMD and NFW models are very similar in terms of reduced χ^2 values.

Fig. 17: As Fig.3 but for DDO50

Fig. 18: As Fig.4 but for DDO50.

Fig. 19: As Fig.3 but for DDO52.

DDO101

DDO101 exhibits a relatively regular LOS velocity field, indicating a coherent velocity pattern within the galaxy. However, both the intensity map and the LOS velocity dispersion maps show significant fluctuations, as depicted in Figures 27-28. The orientation angles in DDO101 demonstrate a roughly constant behavior as a function of radial distance. This suggests a consistent orientation pattern throughout the galaxy, with minimal variations across different regions. The transverse velocity component obtained through the VRM aligns well with the rotational velocity measured by the TRM. In this case the inclination angle from Oh et al. (2015) is very close that determined by Iorio et al. (2017) (i.e., $i = 52^\circ$) and the our determination well agree with both. In this case, because the orientation angles determined by the TRM are nearly constant and exhibit minimal fluctuations, the two profiles are very similar. Both the

NFW and DMD models fit the data equally well, with reduced χ^2 values of 2.5 and 1.4, respectively.

DDO126

Similar to DDO101, DDO126 also exhibits a regular LOS velocity map. The P.A. shows a variation in the inner disc and remains constant as the radial distance from the galactic center increases, as shown in Figures 29-30. In contrast, the inclination angle exhibits a fluctuating behavior with variations of up to ten degrees. When analyzed using the VRM, these variations correspond to significant anisotropies in both velocity components in the outermost regions of the galactic disc. The inclination angle from Oh et al. (2015) is similar to that measured by Iorio et al. (2017) (i.e., $i = 65^\circ$), and thus the different determinations of the circular velocity overlap fairly well.

Fig. 20: As Fig.4 but for DDO52.

Fig. 21: As Fig.3 but for DDO53

Fig. 22: As Fig.4 but for DDO53

These anisotropies indicate directional variations in the velocity components, suggesting complex dynamics in those regions. Both mass model fits are affected by the relatively large fluctuations in the circular velocity component, resulting in a high reduced χ^2 value of 1.7 for the DMD model and 3.0 for the NFW model.

DDO133

The LOS velocity field in DDO133 exhibits irregularities within the inner disc, which appear to be correlated with the structures observed in the intensity distribution, as depicted in Figures 31 - 32. Conversely, the orientation angles display large fluctuations in the inner disc but demonstrate a smooth and constant behavior in the outer regions. The radial and transverse velocity component maps, reconstructed using the VRM, re-

veal significant and localized anisotropies both in the inner and outer regions of the disc. These anisotropies indicate variations in the velocity components in different directions, occurring in specific regions of the galaxy. Even in this case the inclination angle from Oh et al. (2015) is similar to that measured by Iorio et al. (2017) (i.e., $i = 43^\circ$), and thus the different determinations of the circular velocity overlap fairly well but for a difference in the outermost regions of the galaxy where the P.A. shows a variation. Fits with both mass models show good agreement with the data (i.e., $\chi^2 = 0.65$ for the DMD and $\chi^2 = 0.36$ for the NFW), with the main source of variation attributed to the intrinsic fluctuations in the circular velocity profile. .

Fig. 23: As Fig.3 but for DDO70

Fig. 24: As Fig.4 but for DDO70

Fig. 25: As Fig.3 but for DDO87

DDO154

From Figures 33-34, it can be observed that DDO154 exhibits a LOS velocity field that demonstrates the typical pattern expected for a rotating disc. However, while the inclination angle appears nearly flat throughout the entire disc, the position angle (P.A.) shows a decrease with radius in the inner disc, which causes the difference between our determination of the rotational velocity and that measured by Iorio et al. (2017) and Oh et al. (2015). On the other hand, at larger radii, the rotation curves measured by the TRM and the VRM show very similar results. In addition, fluctuations in both orientation angles are observed in the most distant radial bins, suggesting the presence of local anisotropies that become more significant in the outermost regions. This similarity suggests that the warp in DDO154 is not significant. Fits with mass models yield similar

results in terms of the reduced χ^2 , i.e., ~ 1.5 , with the relatively large value being attributed to the outermost data points.

DDO168

DDO168 exhibits a regular LOS velocity map in the inner part of its disc, with an almost aligned kinematic axis (see Figs. 35 - 36). However, the outer regions of the galaxy display irregularities in the LOS velocity distribution. The orientation angles in DDO168 experience relatively large fluctuations but do not exhibit significant radial trends. The inclination angle used in our analysis, i.e., $i = 46.5^\circ$ (Oh et al. 2015), is smaller than that measured by Iorio et al. (2017) (i.e., $i \approx 60^\circ$). In addition, the P.A. shows a radial variation, and these trends cause the relatively small difference between our determination of the circular velocity and theirs.

Fig. 26: As Fig.4 but for DDO87.

Fig. 27: As Fig.3 but for DDO101.

Fig. 28: As Fig.4 but for DDO101.

The transverse and radial component maps reveal localized and substantial anisotropies, indicating variations in the velocity components in different directions within specific regions of the galaxy. Additionally, the radial velocity profile decreases in the external part of the disc, implying a declining trend in the radial velocities towards the outer regions. The determination of the circular velocity using the VRM and TRM methods yields similar results. However, as in other cases, the VRM determination is significantly more fluctuating because the orientation angles are kept fixed. Fitting with mass models yields a reduced χ^2 value around 1.0 in both cases within the radial range [0, 7] kpc. At larger radial distances, the fluctuations become too large to obtain reliable results.

DDO210

In the case of DDO210, the LOS velocity anisotropy field appears irregular, as depicted in Figures 37 and 38. The orientation angles do not exhibit a radial trend, suggesting that the assumption of a flat disc made by the VRM is a good approximation for DDO210. However, they both show relevant fluctuations. For this reason both the radial and transverse velocity component fields show significant anisotropy, particularly in the outermost regions of the galactic disc. These anisotropies indicate variations in the velocity components in different directions, with pronounced effects in specific regions of the galaxy. However, we find a significant discrepancy between our determination of the asymmetric drift and that of Iorio et al. (2017), which is due to the different methods used to measure it. The velocity profiles obtained through the VRM and TRM are very similar, indicating consistency between the two

Fig. 29: As Fig.3 but for DDO126.

Fig. 30: As Fig.4 but for DDO126.

Fig. 31: As Fig.3 but for DDO133.

methods and aligning with the small variation in the orientation angles. This similarity suggests that the warp in DDO210 is not significant and that both methods provide reliable measurements of the rotation curve. There

The NFW model provides a better fit ($\chi^2 = 0.18$) compared to the DMD model ($\chi^2 = 1.3$). This difference arises from the fact that both the stellar and gas profiles are highly fluctuating.

DDO216

Both orientation angles show noticeable fluctuations superimposed on a radial trend toward the outermost part of the disc. These radial changes originate the difference between our determination of the circular velocity and that of Iorio et al. (2017) (see Figures 39-40). Thus, the entire galactic disc is characterized by velocity anisotropies in both components,

which are larger toward the outskirts of the galaxy. These outer regions, where a warp may possibly be present, are not included in the fits for the mass models. The fits with both mass models are comparable and are clearly influenced by the highly fluctuating behavior of the circular velocity.

F564-V3

For the inner galactic disc of F564-V3 (with $R < 100''$), the orientation angles remain relatively constant as a function of radial distance, as shown in Figures 41-42. However, both angles exhibit variations in the outer regions of the galaxy. In particular, the P.A. shows a declining trend, while the inclination angle exhibits large fluctuations. These trends correspond, within the VRM framework, to significant spatial anisotropies and explain the difference between the rotational velocity detected by the

Fig. 32: As Fig.4 but for DDO133.

Fig. 33: As Fig.3 but for DDO154.

Fig. 34: As Fig.4 but for DDO154.

VRM and that measured by the TRM at large radial distances. Since F564-V3 is primarily gas-dominated, a one-parameter fit was performed by varying only the gas component parameter. Consequently, the NFW mass model fit yields a slightly smaller χ^2 .

IC10

The LOS velocity field of IC10 is characterized by extreme irregularities and anisotropy, as shown in Figures 43-44. This velocity field exhibits highly fluctuating and anisotropic behavior, resulting in significant variations in the orientation angles. Although these angles do not show any clear radial dependence, they are marked by substantial fluctuations, which are closely linked to the irregular and anisotropic velocity field identified by the VRM.

In the inner part of the disc, the rotation curve is comparatively more regular but remains affected by considerable fluctuations. Moreover, discrepancies arise between the measurements obtained using the TRM and the VRM, primarily due to the pronounced variations in the orientation angles.

Both mass models yield fits with very small χ^2 values and display nearly identical behavior.

IC1613

IC1613 also exhibits a highly irregular LOS velocity map, as shown in Figures 45 to 46. The orientation angles exhibit a fluctuating behavior. These fluctuations in the orientation angles can be interpreted as significant spatial anisotropies in the velocity field when observed using the VRM. The presence of these fluctuations indicates variations in the velocity

Fig. 35: As Fig.3 but for DDO168.

Fig. 36: As Fig.4 but for DDO168.

Fig. 37: As Fig.3 but for DDO210.

components in different directions within specific regions of the galaxy, contributing to the irregularity observed in the LOS velocity map. Both mass models exhibit excellent agreement with the data.

NGC2366

NGC2366 exhibits an irregular pattern in its LOS velocity field, as depicted in Figures 47 to 48. The orientation angles, in the inner part of the disc, display fluctuations without a clear radial trend. This behavior is consistent with the irregularities observed in the LOS velocity field and with the significant anisotropies detected by the maps reconstructed by the VRM. Due to the lack of a clear radial trend in the orientation angles, it is not surprising that the VRM and the TRM yield similar

results for the rotation velocity. The two mass models provide similarly good fits to the data, with a reduced χ^2 of 0.92.

NGC3738

NGC3738 exhibits an irregular shape and a LOS velocity field characterized by irregular and asymmetrical patterns, as evident from Figures 49 -50. The orientation angles display noticeable fluctuations, indicating the presence of irregularities in the galaxy's dynamics. In particular, the VRM analysis of the velocity components maps shows the presence of anisotropies throughout the disc, indicating variations in the velocity components in different directions within specific regions of the galaxy. However, in the inner disc, the rotational velocities obtained by both the TRM and VRM are similar. For this reason, the fits with the theoretical model are similar, and their rela-

Fig. 38: As Fig.4 but for DDO210.

Fig. 39: As Fig.3 but for DDO216.

Fig. 40: As Fig.4 but for DDO216.

tively high χ^2 values are attributed to the large fluctuations in the observed velocity profile.

WLM

In the case of WLM, the LOS velocity map is relatively more regular and exhibits a nearly symmetrical pattern, as depicted in Figures 51 - 52. The orientation angles show a consistent behavior across all radii, indicating a certain level of uniformity in the galaxy's geometry, i.e. the flat disc assuming is a reasonable one. However, while there is a definitive radial trend, both orientation angles display a fluctuating behavior, which is reflected in the noisy radial profiles of both velocity components when analyzed using the VRM. The velocity components maps obtained through the VRM analysis reveal moderate anisotropies in the inner disc and more significant

anisotropies in the outermost regions. Both mass models provide a reasonable fit to the data, with comparable χ^2 values.

Fig. 41: As Fig.3 but for F564-V3.

Fig. 42: As Fig.4 but for F564-V3.

Fig. 43: As Fig.3 but for IC10.

Fig. 44: As Fig.4 but for IC10.

Fig. 45: As Fig.3 but for IC1613.

Fig. 46: As Fig.4 but for IC1613.

Fig. 47: As Fig.3 but for NGC2366.

Fig. 48: As Fig.4 but for NGC2366.

Fig. 49: As Fig.3 but for NGC3738.

Fig. 50: As Fig.4 but for NGC3738.

Fig. 51: As Fig.3 but for WLM.

Fig. 52: As Fig.4 but for WLM.